

**BACILLUS AVLODIGA MANSUB BAKTERIYALARNING
BIOTEXNOLOGIK POTENSIALI**

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Annotatsiya: Zamburug'li patogenlar atrof-muhitdagi o'simliklar dinamikasining muhim omilidir. Bu patogenlar o'simliklarning o'limiga olib kelishi mumkin va tuproqdagi dastlabki zichlik past bo'lsa ham, vaqti-vaqti bilan ekinlarda hosilni yo'qotadi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi tanlash va baholash edi zamburug'li antagonistik bakteriyalar va ularning soya ko'chatlarida biologik nazorat qilish qobiliyatini aniqlash. dan jami 877 shtamlari Pseudomonas, Bacillus va Paraburkholderia/Burkholderia avlodlari va ularning zamburug'larga antagonistik ta'siri tekshirildi. Urug'larda tez-tez topilganlar to'rtta usul yordamida baholandi: to'rt marta qoplama, juftlashgan madaniyat qarama-qarshiligi, shtammni ushlab turish, va soya urug'ini ekish. Eksperimental dizayn butunlay tasodifiy bo'lib, dastlabki uchtasi uchun uchta takrorlash bilan usullari va to'rtinchi davolash uchun 3×9 faktorial sxemada besh replikatsiya. Eng yuqori biotexnologik shtammlar Soya urug'iga unib chiqqanda bu ekinga hujum qiladigan zamburug'larning biologik nazoratini baholash uchun potentsial emlangan. Etmish to'qqizta shtamm sinovdan o'tgan qo'ziqorinlarga qandaydir antagonistik ta'sir ko'rsatdi, ikkita shtamm esa kengroq ta'sir ko'rsatdi. urug 'testidagi antagonistik ta'sir spektri. Antagonistik potentsialga qo'shimcha ravishda, BR 10788 va BR 11793 shtamlari, qachon bir vaqtning o'zida yoki yolg'iz emlangan, fide quruq moddalar massasini sezilarli darajada oshirdi va soya o'sishini rag'batlantirdi.

ko'chatlar ko'pchilik zamburug'lar mavjudligida ham. Shunday qilib, ushbu tadqiqot ularning antagonistik faoliyati samaradorligini ko'rsatdi biologik nazorat uchun potentsial agentlar ekanligi isbotlangan maqsadli qo'ziqorinlarga nisbatan shtammlar.

Kalit soʻzlar: Pseudomonas, Bacillus, Paraburkholderia/Burkholderia, Colletotrichum kiradi spp., Fusarium spp., Aspergillus spp., Cercospora spp., Penicillium sp., Alternaria spp., Cladosporium sp.

Kirish

Zamburug'li patogenlar qishloq xo'jaligi sharoitida o'simliklar populyatsiyasining dinamikasini belgilovchi omillardir. Soya uchun, misollar Iqtisodiy ahamiyatga ega patogenlar qatoriga Colletotrichum kiradi spp., Fusarium spp., Aspergillus spp., Cercospora spp., Penicillium sp., Alternaria spp., Cladosporium sp., O'simlikka olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan Sclerotinia spp., va Rhizoctonia spp o'lim va vaqti-vaqti bilan past boshlang'ich tuproqda ham hosilning umumiy yo'qolishi inokulum zichligi Patogenlarni kamaytirish uchun biologik vositalardan foydalanish bo'lgan samarali, istiqbolli va keng o'rganilgan usul ekanligi ko'rsatilgan [4-6]. Biroq, mumkin bo'lgan kasalliklar soni bo'lsa-da biologik nazorat qilinishi amaliy jihatdan ahamiyatli, kam biologik mahsulotlar aslida ishlatilgan. Buning sababi patogenlar tomonidan qo'yilgan cheklovlar va ularning muvaffaqiyatsizligi tanlash tartibi, atrof-muhit omillari, texnik muammolar va tajriba tizimidagi strategiyalar [7]. Yangi foydalanish uchun mikroorganizmlarni tanlash jarayoni O'simlik qo'ziqorinining patogen jinslarini bionazorat qilish uchun tijorat mahsulotlari murakkab, chunki keyingi bosqichlarning muvaffaqiyati uchun hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan tahlil qilinadigan bir qancha mezonlar mavjud. Bular orasida antagonistik samaradorlik, qarama-qarshilik mexanizmlari, adekvat aholini saqlaydigan transport vositasining o'sishi va hatto qonuniy mulk huquqlarini ta'minlash tartiblari va bozorga kirish juda muhimdir [8]

Bakteriyalar shtammlarining filogeniyasi

Har birida turli tur guruhlar bilan bog'liqlikga asoslangan filogenetik tahlil yo'li bilan jins olingan Shtammlar va turdagi shtammlarning 16S rRNK gen ketma-ketligi. Tahlil uchun qo'shni-qo'shilish usuli ishlatilgan va Har bir jins uchun eng mos modellar

(Pseudomonas: Kimura ikki parametr; Bacillus: Tamura-Nei; Paraburkholderia/Burkholderia: Tamura uchta parametr)MEGA dasturi yordamida (versiya 7.0). Eng yaqin tur bacterio.net da tasvirlangan har bir jinsdagi shtammlar platformasi (<http://www.bacterio.net/methylophilus.html>) edi hisobga olinadi. Klasterlar asosida turlar ichiga joylashtirilgann tegishli guruhlar

Natijalar va muhokama

Petrida qo'ziqorinlarga bakterial antagonizmni baholash idishlar

Hammasi bo'lib 877 shtamm filogenetik jihatdan o'rganildi Pseudomonas, Bacillus va nasldagi 16S rRNK Paraburkholderiya / Burkholderiya. Shtammlar izolyatsiya qilingan Braziliya va ikkala xost va substratlardan kelib chiqqan, masalan ildizlari, dukkakli o'simliklar tugunlari va o'simlik rizosferasi Guruhlardan 32 ta navlar tanlab olindi Pseudomonas va Bacillus va 37 jinsdan Paraburkholderia/Burkholderia jami 101 shtammni tashkil etuvchi alohida filogenetik guruhlarni ifodalaydi

Soya urug'lari ishtirokida fitopatogenlarga qarshi bioassay inokulyantlarining antagonistik salohiyati

Zamburug'lar	BR 10788 BR 11793 Antagonizm (%)* F.	BR 11793	Aralash	Anglatadi
F. semitectum	86.7 aA	93.3 aA	100.0 aA	93.3 a
F. piperis	80.8 aA	100.0 aA	89.6 aA	90.2 a
P. sojæ	57.8 bA 85.6 aA 68.3 aA 70.6 b	57.8 bA 85.6 aA 68.3 aA 70.6 b	57.8 bA 85.6 aA 68.3 aA 70.6 b	57.8 bA 85.6 aA 68.3 aA 70.6 b
C. cassicola	52.6 bA 27.2 bA 55.9 bA 45.2 c	52.6 bA 27.2 bA 55.9 bA 45.2 c	52.6 bA 27.2 bA 55.9 bA 45.2 c	52.6 bA 27.2 bA 55.9 bA 45.2 c

A.flavus	21.1 cB 86.5 aA 58.3 bA 55.3 c			
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Misol uchun, AQShda B.subtilis dan tayyorlangan mahsulotlar 1983 yildan beri yeryong'oq urug'ini davolash va barglar uchun ishlatiladi va tuproq ilovalari. Bundan tashqari, B. subtilis ham ishlatiladi Fusarium solguniga qarshi faol urug'larni davolash, P. damping-off, va Cercospora, Colletotrichum sabab bo'lgan barglar dog'lari, Alternaria, Ascochyta, Myrothecium, Ramularia, Hindistonda paxta, don, sabzavot, meva va bezak o'simliklarida Xanthomonas va Erysiphe poligonlari. Uning harakati asosan sabab bo'ladi antibiotiklar ishlab chiqarishga, kosmos uchun raqobat va ozuqa moddalari, antibiotiklar va hujayra devorining degradatsiyasi. Shunday qilib, mahsulotlar uchun vosita bo'lib xizmat qiluvchi antagonistik mikroorganizmlarga asoslangan fitopatogenlarni nazorat qilish

Xulosa

BR 10788 va BR 11793 shtammlari samaradorlikni ko'rsatdi zamburug'lar. BR 10788 va BR bakteriyalarining kombinatsiyasi qo'ziqorin nazorati qobiliyatini teng yoki undan yuqori ko'rsatdi individual shtammlarga. O'rganilgan bioagentlar kamaytirishi mumkin qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari urug'larini davolashda fungitsidlardan foydalanishsoya urug'larini fitopatogenlarga qarshi davolash mumkin.

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